

The Importance of Decision-Making Mechanisms in Business When It comes to Subjective Experience of Uncertainty Forms and MNC Management on Uncertainties

Murat Erkan

To cite this article: Murat Erkan, Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 405 – 424. - 0099-0001-2209-0514.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

- The magazine is published monthly.

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Research has shown that certain individual decision makers may have a different perception of certain uncertainties than the rest of MNC management, or may not recognize them at all (Kiss, Williams, & Houghton, 2013). Therefore, more research involving subjective measures of uncertainty is needed to understand how decision makers in multinational companies (MNCs) truly distinguish and respond to various aspects of uncertainty. Results from subjective assessments of uncertainty are more likely to be indicative of what individual decision-makers actually experience (as in, for example, Petersen et al., 2008 or Whitelock & Jobber, 2004). According to the findings of a recent study conducted by Haley, more than eighty percent of managers working in multinational companies use qualitative human judgments to assess the level of uncertainty, while less than twenty percent rely on statistical methods (2003). Therefore, the inclusion of more subjective measures of uncertainty can give a more accurate representation of how multinational companies understand and rank various types of uncertainty. That is, potential topics for future study could address any of the following types of problems: How diverse are the perspectives of MNC decision makers when it comes to the subjective experience of various forms of uncertainty? What ground does this heterogeneity provide for coming together at the MNC level? How do heterogeneity and homogeneity in people's perceptions of uncertainty affect decision making? By combining the conceptual and statistically more parsimonious aspects of uncertainty and using more subjective measures, it is possible to increase the predictive efficiency of various theoretical models of MNC behavior under uncertainty environments.

Keywords: *Subjective Experience of Uncertainty Forms, Decision Making Mechanisms, Business Decision Making, MNC Management*

1. Introduction

Addressing the problem of lack of diversity in aspects of uncertainty involved in single studies A second weakness of current IB research is that studies tend to focus on uncertainties in only one category (eg, environmental or industrial category) . Although there has been a shift from various categories towards integrating uncertainties (for example, Beckman et al., 2004; Brouthers et al.,

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

2008; Galang , 2012; Henisz & Delios , 2001; Liu & Maula , 2016), the vast majority of studies combine uncertainties within the same study. rather than in parallel. This is a major flaw due to the fact that focusing on a single uncertainty, such as political uncertainty, can lead to misinformed entry-mode judgments if other uncertainties are ignored (e.g., Brouthers , 1995). Studies based on empirical evidence have shown significant links between one or more features of uncertainty and the mode of entry chosen by MNCs (Ahmed, Mohamad , Tan, & Johnson, 2002). However, the interconnections that exist between the various types of uncertainty and the implications of these interconnections on uncertainty management and decision making are still largely unexplored in IB research. For example, company-level uncertainties are not given as much attention in IB research as the environmental and industry aspects of uncertainty (See Figure 2). According to the strategy tripod model (Peng , Wang, & Jiang, 2008), the strategic choices made by MNCs are influenced by environmental, industry, and firm-specific variables. Consequently, uncertainties in all three categories should be treated equally. Within the IB area, the strategic decision-making activities that have gained the majority of the work are those related to location and mode of entry considerations. However, the results of this comprehensive review of the relevant literature suggest that the majority of research that analyzes these choices focuses on investigating the impact of environmental or industrial uncertainty, essentially minimizing the role played by firm uncertainties.

2. On Operational Preferences

multinational companies (MNCs), a similar trend emerges: the firm dimensions of uncertainty are often overlooked. If we exclude a wider range of uncertainty from individual studies, we cannot see the links that exist between them, and only insufficient justification is provided for decisions made by MNCs . The inclusion of several dimensions not only helps to solve this problem, but also gives a closer picture of the practical reality that decision makers in MNCs have to face. While IB research appears to be more concerned with environmental or industrial uncertainty, MNCs are believed to be more focused on addressing company uncertainties in international decision-making. This is an example of such a difference. According to the observations made by Buckley,

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Devinney , and Louviere (2007), multinational companies aiming to operate in foreign operations often follow theoretically predictable trajectories. On the other hand, the actual implementation of these tasks is less compatible with traditional models.

3. Time to Take Decisions into Action

As the authors explain, when it's time to take decisions into action, decision makers tend to pay more and less attention to uncertainties about the firm itself (such as return on investment, cost of production, use and protection of assets). International decision-making models will not only gain an enhanced ability to explain the type of MNC behavior change observed, but will also open up opportunities to examine the interactions between the various types of uncertainty implied above, in addition to the firm dimensions of uncertainty. Environmental and sectoral uncertainties are taken into account in the models. This will not only improve the models' ability to explain the type of MNC behavioral variation observed, but will also improve the models' ability to explain why some MNCs occur . This is because MNCs operate in highly complex business environments. However, it is important to understand not only how one category of uncertainty is handled, but also how the simultaneous impact of many uncertainties arising from various categories affects how MNC operations are and should be managed. Consequently, future work should focus on answering the following categories of study questions:

In the process of making international decisions, decision makers often focus their attention on a number of different aspects of uncertainty. Why is this so and how does this affect the choices made? What strategies do multinational companies (MNCs) use to manage uncertainty when faced with a wide variety of uncertainties in various fields , and do these strategies change according to the nature of the uncertainties they face?

Some scholars make more targeted inquiries such as:

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

"Does multi-level interaction of variables at the nation, industry, firm, and project levels affect entry selection? Both external and internal antecedents of entry mode selection actually result in higher performance?" (Luo , 2001, page 467) and "In addition to industry-level variables, firm and country-level features, three types of MNC entry methods (i.e. buy-from-scratch, purchase, joint venture)?" (Luo , 2001, p. 467) (Elango & Sambharya , 2004, p. 121).

There are a number of different courses of action that an action plan or strategy can take in any business situation. Establishing an efficient decision-making process is an essential component of successfully managing company operations, especially in large companies, as there are many different options to consider and many to continually consider. There are many different approaches to decision making, but most have at least five common stages:

- *Identify a challenge the company is facing.*
- *Investigate the many options available and the likely impacts these choices will have.*
- *Consider all the options and choose one to continue.*
- *Enforce the selection as the firm is managed.*
- *Keep an eye on the situation, collect data on how the election turned out, and be prepared to make adjustments if necessary.*

4. Data-Based Decision Making

In the past, choices were traditionally made by corporate leaders and company executives based on their intuitive understanding of the circumstances surrounding the issue in question. On the other hand, intuitive decision making has a number of downsides. For example, an instinctive approach makes it difficult to justify decisions after the facts and bases institutional decision-making on the experience and accumulated knowledge of individuals who may be vulnerable to cognitive biases that lead them to make bad decisions. In addition, instinctive approaches base institutional decision -making on the experience and accumulated knowledge of individuals. Therefore, modern firms often make decisions using methods that are more methodical and data-driven. This makes it possible for managers and executives to defend their judgments using

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

methods such as cost-benefit analysis and predictive modelling. Additionally, it enables different lines of business to create process automation protocols that can be applied to new situations as they arise, eliminating the need to treat each as a unique decision-making event. It also makes it possible to implement these protocols in multiple business areas. A methodical approach to decision making, if well designed, makes it less likely that people's innate biases and blind spots will lead to less effective outcomes than those in decision making.

On the other hand, data is not perfect, so monitoring the effects of elections on a company's operations is a crucial step in case things go wrong. Instead of blindly following where the data is going, it is necessary to follow the analytics and decision-making phases as it is possible for people to choose the wrong data. This underlines the need to monitor these stages. Barriers in decision-making Finding a happy medium between using one's intuition and making evidence-based decisions is a challenging prospect. It is possible for managers and executives to be reluctant to base their decision making on evidence that contradicts their instincts, especially if they have the impression that their years of experience and expertise have been minimized or completely ignored. As a result, they may argue against the results produced by business intelligence (BI) and analytics technologies throughout the decision-making process .

It is not always easy to get everyone together about the choices that must be made for a company, especially if the decision-making process is not transparent and the decisions are not communicated very effectively to those who will be affected by it, it is a good choice as well as a change management strategy to deal with the consequences of the decisions on the firm's operations. requires the creation of an internal communication plan about elections. Decision-making models can also be used to avoid these numerous problems in the first place by creating an organized and transparent process. A decision-making model is a method or procedure that people can follow or copy to ensure that they choose the most advantageous option from a range of potential alternatives . The decision-making process can be simplified with the help of a model as it provides rules that help organizations reach a positive outcome . The decision-making process is made transparent and easily communicated to all relevant parties, including all managers, stakeholders and personnel, thanks to the use of decision models . They're useful across

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

departments, businesses, and industries for a wide variety of reasons, but they're especially useful when choosing software suppliers or new tools, deciding on new action plans, or implementing changes that affect a significant number of people.

5. Various Decision Making Frameworks and Paradigms

Models based on rational thinking are among the most common types used in decision making. The model with the highest adoption level is the rational decision-making process. It follows a logical and linear progression, with the primary emphasis being the enumeration of as many potential courses of action as possible by the human. When all possibilities are distributed, it is possible to evaluate them to decide which is most advantageous. In these models, alternatives are usually specified in order of convenience, with the respective benefits and disadvantages for each alternative. The following procedures are commonly found in any rational decision-making model:

- *Determine if the problem is a problem or an opportunity.*
- *Identify and evaluate criteria for making a choice .*
- *Gather and organize all relevant information.*
- *Do some research on the subject. Create a number of different alternatives.*
- *Evaluate all possibilities and give each one a point.*
- *Determine which of the options is preferable.*
- *Put choice into action.*
- *Evaluate the choice made.*

6. Intuitive Models

The basic premise of these decision-making models is that there is no logic or reason involved in the decision-making process. Rather, the process is determined by an inner knowing, often known as intuition, about which choice represents the best course of action. On the other hand, intuitive

CURRENT SCIENCE

models are not entirely dependent on one's instincts. In addition, they consider awareness of patterns and similarities, as well as the importance or importance of choice.

7. Recognition Lined Models

These theories represent a synthesis of logical thinking and instinctive instinct for decision making. The feature that distinguishes this approach from others is that the person making the choice evaluates only one alternative instead of evaluating all alternatives. The following steps are performed in the recognition-preparatory decision-making process:

- *all aspects of the problem, including problem clues, expectations, and business goals .*
- *Go through the plan step by step and simulate it in your head to see if it will work and what adjustments are likely to be needed.*
- *If the plan is deemed sufficient, a final decision is made and the strategy is put into practice.*
- *In models based on recognition priming, alternative courses of action are considered only if the initial strategy does not produce the desired results.*

There is a direct relationship between the experience and skill level of the individual and the success rate of this approach. According to the decision-making model presented here, users get facts and insights about the problem at hand and offer some preliminary suggestions for possible solutions. After that, the person responsible for making the choice enters a phase known as "incubation", where it does not actively consider alternatives. Instead, they let their subconscious minds guide them through the process, which eventually results in a revelation and a response that they can then confirm and approve of.

At the same time, the manager, who usually owns it, must have management responsibilities such as decision making, interpersonal relations or knowledge. An entrepreneur who is a conflict resolver, resource allocator, negotiator, leader, coordinator, representative and observer must also be able to think strategically and have a visionary mindset. There is no established template for

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

the strategic decision-making process in small firms. Decision making is simplified, passes through only a few layers of management and is therefore more centralized. Additionally, it does not need elaborate formal processes, bureaucratic records, or paperwork. A great deal of work and complexity is required to implement equal treatment, particularly in the areas of communication and coordination. When it comes to collecting, processing and interpreting huge volumes of information that is sometimes unclear, small businesses often have only a few employees working on these tasks. But it is important to grasp this information. To accommodate the specific elements of strategic decision making in small firms discussed above, it is necessary to change the generally applicable strategic decision making models and methods to accommodate these constraints.

There are several distinct differences between model approaches to strategic decision-making. The degree of application of reason and integrity on the one hand, and the use of managers' intuition and experience on the other, are the criteria commonly used to evaluate management. The vast majority of managers are confident that their options make sense, and as a result, they strive to make consistent decisions while maximizing value within predetermined limits. A full awareness of decision makers is a prerequisite for objective rationality, which is a prerequisite of rationality-based normative theory. The person who will make the choice should be able to determine the selection preferences and these preferences should be consistent. To effectively address the problem, it is essential to explore all possible solutions and gather all relevant information. Because of these assumptions, one of the variants provides the greatest possible benefit. An economically sensible asset is constantly trying to find the most effective answer to the challenge at hand in order to increase the amount of money it brings.

8. Modeling Strategy

Achieving objective rationality requires recognizing the limited rationality that results from making unreasonable assumptions. In addition, the need for decision makers to fully understand all possible variations and the implications of each of these variants, as well as the weak relationship that exists between knowledge and final choice, is also tedious. As a result, bounded

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

rationality is thinking about dealing with information that the decision maker believes is sufficient and correct. Social rationality is a component of bounded rationality. This rationality incorporates aspects of ethics into the decision-making process . and emphasizes ethical considerations as satisfactory and satisfactory for the decision. It is also known as formal rationality and requires adherence to a set of standards made up of representatives of decision makers. The satisfaction principle is applied with a limited rational approach when the manager is not trying to achieve maximum effect but to arrive at a satisfactory solution that is superior to what was initially expected. Creating additional options requires little effort. Especially in the case of micro-owners, managers may not always directly represent the goals of the company and tend to be more self-interested than economic considerations. Behavior like this is described as "satisfied with goals", which leads to a reluctance to implement adjustments in his company . These decisions involve choosing from a set of alternatives that have already been outlined, and the effects of these alternatives can be both determined and calculated. On the other hand, the wide application of rationality in strategic decision-making is questioned and rationalized by the unique characteristics of strategic decision-making and the inability to apply many methods especially in the conditions of uncertainty and difficulty of the external environment. This is because certain features of strategic decision making and the inapplicability of many methods are rationalized by specific features of strategic decision making . This is where both intuition and experience come into play. Heuristics are used when it comes to making strategic choices about people, identifying environmental risks, and seeking opportunities in new circumstances. This is especially true where the most effective ideas are required. In the field of strategy, strategic intuition is equated in importance with strategic analysis and strategic planning. Another factor is that there are no longer managers who focus on "facts". This reality gives rise to the urge to use experiential approaches called "experiential management" as well as ways tailored to specific circumstances. Especially among micro-business managers, there is a tendency to blend randomly acquired knowledge, heuristics, and other mental shortcuts into intuitive decision-making processes. In addition to the model approaches mentioned (rational, bound-rational, and heuristic), there are other approaches in the business literature that try to combine or extend the above-mentioned approaches or

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

incorporate other factors into models . strategic decision making process. Hitt and Tyler divided the strategic decision-making process into three different conceptual models:

- *Rational-normative model that supports the use of objective index figures in strategic decision making and emerges from both internal and internal analysis. and external business environment.*
- *Another is called the strategic choice model and results from limited rationality throughout the strategic decision making process.*

This shows that the personality of the manager as well as the subjective influence of management is the primary factor. The last model is called the external control model and emphasizes the role played by an organization's external environment in strategic decision making. Choosing a favorite among these options is not a simple undertaking that strains your imagination. Even the authors themselves seem to think that the trend is moving towards integrating all the previously discussed models . Elbanna and Child constructed an integrated model of the rationality of strategic decision making. This model consists of three aspects that influence rationality: the nature of the environment, the work, and the decision-making process itself. Calabretta et al. similarly regard rational and intuitive inputs as paradoxical thinking that produces results through paradoxical thinking rather than an alternative choice operation. Time constraints and the complexity of the surrounding environment were two factors Rahman and De Feis used to categorize different model approaches to strategic decision making.

The Dustbin Model is based on the absence of traditional problem-to-solution decision making; mutual separation of problems and solutions; the tendency for businesses to produce many solutions that are rejected for lack of problems and then repeatedly rejected because of searching for "trash cans"; Decisions are the results of a stream of serious decisions made one after another. According to the findings of several academic studies, the two model methods listed above are those used by small companies and micro-enterprises when it comes to the process of making strategic decisions. Treffers and Klarner analyze emotions and decision making for strategic change under time pressure. They present their findings, which they argue that negative emotions,

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

rather than positive ones, influence strategic decision-making, and that their effects vary across decision-making stages.

Additionally, it shows that these effects differ depending on the decision-making stage. His research contributes to the fields of strategy implementation and strategy process research by incorporating the expression of emotions as embodied practices into the process of making strategic decisions. Kaufmann et al, logical processing is the most important factor, while heuristic modes play an important supporting role.

As managers process and evaluate information, they tracked their answers to the question of obtaining information that preceded it. Extensive databases, statistical and quantitative analysis, both financial and expert level reports, etc. The absence of tools for The challenge of effective decision making can also stem from the fact that managers are overflowing with information and fail to understand it and not be able to properly assist the decision making process because they cannot handle the volume of data. As a result of the findings of our research, we came to the conclusion that the material was not presented correctly or clearly. A large number of managers continue to manage and make decisions as if there was no global computer network. This issue can be approached from several different angles. To begin with, there is an excessive reliance on direct intuition, which is often confirmed by the extensive expertise of managers. Second, there is a very weak correlation between the pieces of information actually available to management and the choice it makes. This is because the information the administrator can actually access is limited. In the end, such evaluations ignore familiar, time-bound procedures as well as favor the institution. Most small businesses do not have a clear understanding of what actions are most beneficial to their operations and do not know how to use information and new technology to make their decisions more informed. Our findings are consistent with the results of previous studies that highlighted the lack of analytics-based managers, the tendency to use an ad hoc method, the use of an experience-based strategy, and behavioral evidence. Another aspect of the study focused on the strategic decision-making process in small businesses. The feedback makes it clear that the heuristic model is the dominant paradigm. Managers often make decisions without appearing to use all relevant information available from their memories and the surrounding environment. This

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

can occur daily. Although they are aware of all the information, they do not always give them the appropriate amount of priority and do not always delve into it before making a choice. On the other hand, they are usually interested in the first thing that comes to mind. In most cases, they make no visible effort and are unable to provide a satisfactory explanation when asked why they have made such a suggestion. Managers often tend to believe it, as using their instincts can be extremely productive in some situations.

They seem to be able to achieve satisfaction by using intuition in various contexts. Undoubtedly, we need to emphasize a positive impression of intuitive decision-making, especially among managers of small companies. These individuals do not have the luxury of time to rationally and methodically evaluate all available options. They are trained to make judgments in a specific method that has proven effective and saves time up to this point. They assess the situation using previous experience and links to various other designs. They act almost quickly, based on their experience and intuition. Simplicity, speed and parallelism are the three main benefits. However, changing one's thinking is very difficult and time consuming. It is possible, but not guaranteed, that intuitive judgments are accurate and within control. It is deeply influenced by a wide variety of dispositions, habits, abbreviations, and heuristics.

In this particular scenario, the most effective way to exercise control over one's intuitive judgments is to engage in more time- and labor-intensive logical mental processes. This is why many writers bring this up when citing counter-arguments [26-28] and at other times throughout their work. He goes on to say that although intuitive thinking has a role in decision making, "anyone who believes that intuition has replaced rational thinking is a dangerous commitment to self-deception." "Intuition is an unpredictable and autonomous leader who can lead you to immediate success, but just as quickly to terrible disaster."

Consequently, in order to make intuitive judgments, it is necessary to have years of experience as well as to learn the many facts, scenarios, ideas, processes and abstractions stored in the human brain. Intuitive methods, lapses of reason, or the emotions of managers have the potential to suffocate the entire decision-making process and lead them to the wrong conclusion. Because of the way the research was structured, analyzing managers' behavioral patterns in terms of their

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

cognitive, emotional, and other socially conditioned tendencies was not an overly challenging task. If the aim of the study is to gain a deeper knowledge, it is desirable to make individual choices in a smaller number of businesses with a wide array of problems. This can be accomplished by selecting firms. It is likely to happen throughout the process of making a choice, and when it does, it opens the door to the possibility of different and unique effects of emotions, personality traits, heuristics, prejudices, aberrations, ethical principles.

In order to evaluate the above-mentioned patterns, several questions were asked to the managers. In order to avoid misunderstanding of the intended importance of the questions, the collection of answers was carried out in a directed interview format. "Would you rather have someone else's experience or the advice of an outside consultant?" It included questions such as Which scenario appeals to you more: a profitable sale of the company or a continuation of the venture so that you can achieve your personal goals? Would you rather hire cheaper workers from other countries, even if it means doing so at the expense of domestic workers? Do you make a choice when under a lot of pressure, or try to put it off until a later time? Have you ever thought about what the outcome of a choice you've made before would have been if you had gone a different route?

When negotiating, do you prepare specific suggestions before the meeting or do you wait for the opinions of the other party? Do any of the myriad events, trends or outdated information from the past have an impact on the decisions you make? When faced with a choice, do you consider making a decision later, perhaps the next day, or do you make a decision and act immediately? Is it possible to avoid the costs embedded in your choices, whether financial or psychological? When collecting information, have you ever thought about whether you give more weight to pieces of information that confirm your statement or pieces of information that contradict it?

After analyzing the responses given by the managers, we realized that the above-mentioned aspects of the decision-making process can have a noticeable impact on the outcome. It shows that an intuitive decision-making model dominates, which correlates with their intuitive strategic thinking. Intuitive strategic thinking is defined as thinking that works according to the main item, and the integrity is evaluated according to a selected central element.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

9. Conclusion

Unlike simple, routine decisions made to gain an advantage over competitors, strategic decisions are often difficult in nature and aim to change both the overall scope of authority and the direction of the business. It is relevant in many areas and, given the enormous impact of strategic choices on the performance of the latter, the efficient recruitment of their staff is of the utmost importance to both large and small businesses. Although there are significant differences in the way strategic decisions are made in large and small businesses, much of the research and work has focused primarily on large companies and continues to focus. Therefore, it is difficult for small businesses to benefit from theory and research conducted by large businesses. We were able to validate our stated research questions through actual research. At the same time, aspects of a limited rational model approach seem to be combined with certain features of an ascending and descending strategic decision-making model. Limited rationality isn't always a bad thing when it comes to small businesses; however, this is also a result of the lack of quantitative analysis, low level of expertise and use of analytical tools, making it a potentially problematic situation. The answer to the second study question is that the customer base is the most important element that plays a formative role in the strategic decision-making process in small businesses. In addition, the third research question focused on the impact of experience, ethical considerations, emotions, personal characteristics, and subliminal information processing in making strategic decisions. Small companies make strategic decisions through a process that can be defined as an unsystematic, random and passive search for information, most of which comes from the external environment. This can result in acceptable or "fairly good" decisions being accepted, as opposed to decisions that have the potential to have the greatest impact. The values and ethical judgments that managers make are based on their previous experiences, which are influenced by their feelings and emotions. They unconsciously make judgments based on their knowledge and expertise. After examining the theoretical basis and the findings of the study, we are able to identify the primary factors that influence and shape the process by which small business managers arrive at strategic decisions, as illustrated in Diagram 1.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

10. References

- Aharoni, Y. (1966). The foreign investment decision process. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School. [Crossref], [Google Scholar]
- Aharoni, Y., Tihanyi, L., & Connelly, BL (2011). Managerial decision-making in international business: A forty-five-year retrospective. *Journals of World Business*, 46, 135–142. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2010.05.001> [Crossref], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar]
- Ahmed, ZU, Mohamad, O., Tan, B., & Johnson, JP (2002). International risk perceptions and mode of entry: A case study of Malaysian multinational firms. *Journal of Business Research*, 55, 805–813. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(00\)00220-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(00)00220-4)
- Ahsan, M., & Musten, M. (2011). Multinational enterprises' entry mode strategies and uncertainty: A review and extension. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 13, 376–392.
- Akhter, SH, & Choudhry, YA (1993). Forced withdrawal from a country market: Managing political risk. *Business Horizons*, 36, 47–54. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813\(05\)80148-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0007-6813(05)80148-X)
- Akhter, SH, & Robles, F. (2006). Leveraging internal competency and managing environmental uncertainty. *International Marketing Review*, 23(1), 98–115. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/02651330610646313>
- Alderson, P., Green, S., & Higgins, J. (2004). *Cochrane reviewer's handbook*. Chichester, UK: Wiley.
- Forsgren , M. (1989). *Managing the Internationalization Process—The Swedish Case*. London: Routledge.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

- Gray, RJ (2001). Organizational climate and project success. *International Journal of Project Management*, 19, 103–109.
- Hoogervorst, J., Flier, H., & Koopman, P. (2004). Implicit communication in organizations : the impact of culture, structure and management practices. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 19, 288–311.
- Longman, A. & Guttman, HM (2006). Project teams: how good are they? *Quality Progress*, 39, 59–65.
- Luecke, R. (2003). *Managing change in transition*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Morrison, JM, Brown, CJ, & Smit, E. (2008). The impact of organizational culture on project management in matrix organizations. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 39, 27–36.
- Morrison, JM, Brown, CJ, & Smith, E. (2006). A supportive organizational culture for project management in matrix organisations : A theoretical perspective. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 37, 39–54.
- Office of Government Commerce (OGC) (2007). *Managing Successful Programs*. (Third ed.) London: TSO (The Stationery Office).
- Pellegrinelli, S., Partington, D., Hemingway, C., Mohdzain, Z., & Shah, M. (2007). The importance of context in program management: An empirical review of program practices. *International Journal of Project Management*, 25, 41–55.
- Pettigrew, AM, McKee, L., & Ferlie, E. (1992). *Shaping strategic change making change in large organizations: the case of the National Health Service*. London: Sage Publications.
- Rousseau DM, Mc. Carthy S. Evidence-based management: Educating managers from an evidence-based perspective. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*. 2007;6(1):94-101
- Subjective Experience of Uncertainty Forms, Decision Making Mechanisms, Business Decision Making, MNC Management forest.H. and Hunt. JM

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

(2005). Managing the influence of internal and external determinants on international industrial pricing strategies. Industrial Marketing Managemnet , 34, 133-146.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | **RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY** PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE